

A Comprehensive Study on Sustained Release Matrix Tablets of Tofacitinib Citrate

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Abstract

The aim of this study was the formulation and characterization of a sustained- release matrix tablet by perfecting the dissolution rate of Tofacitinib Citrate and release the drug in controlled manner. The sustained release expression provides important way to drop the side effect of drug by precluding change of remedial attention of drug in body. In the present study, HPMC was applied as the matrix forming polymer for the sustained release of tofacitinib. The relationship between the drug and excipients was studied and selected. Matrix tablets were manufactured by direct compression method. The flowability of the material was estimated by determining their bulk density, tapped density, angle of repose, Hausner rate, and carr's index. Compressed tablets were tested for their physical parameters, drug content, and in vitro drug release, as per United States Pharmacopeia (USP). Tofacitinib citrate is compatible with all the excipients used in the expression of polymeric matrix tablets. The FTIR spectrum of tofacitinib citrate verified the compatibility of tofacitinib and other constituents of the matrix tablets. Physically, matrix tablets were smooth, glossy and free of defects. HPMC successfully sustained the medicine release for 24 hours. This study concluded from the study that dissolution rate of tofacitinib citrate can be sustained using hydrophilic polymer (HPMC) as a release controlling agent [1].

Keywords: Tofacitinib citrate, sustained release, HPMC, matrix, rheumatoid arthritis

Introduction

Sustained drug delivery systems are utilized to create a continuous therapeutic effect over a lengthy period of time. The sustained drug delivery system minimizes the frequency of dosing [2]. Tofacitinib citrate is a new type of therapy known as a Janus kinase (JAK) inhibitor. Tofacitinib citrate is used to treat rheumatoid arthritis, psoriasis, and ulcerative colitis. Tofacitinib is available in three forms: tablets, extended-release tablets, and oral solution. There is an acute need for several types of tofacitinib formulations to treat severe cases of arthritis.

The Pubchem catalog shows the molecular formula of tofacitinib citrate as C₂₂H₂₈N₆O₈ and the molecular weight as 504.5 g/mol. The chemical name of tofacitinib citrate is 2-hydroxypropane-1,2,3-tricarboxylic acid 3-[(3R,4R)-4-methyl-3-[methyl(7H-pyrrolo[2,3-d]pyrimidin-4-yl)amino]piperidin-1-yl]-3-oxopropionitrile [3].

The chemical structure of tofacitinib citrate is represented in fig. 1.

Fig 1: Chemical structure of Tofacitinib Citrate

Fig 2: 3D structure of Tofacitinib

In the past few years, pharmaceutical scientists have used many strategies to control the amount of drugs in the blood. The simplest and most effective way is to stimulate the release of the drug to ensure that the drug remains in the blood for a longer period of time. The additional release agents remain in the digestive tract and ensure that the drug is released at a rate equal to the elimination, thus ensuring that the desired drug remains in the blood for a long time. The main purpose of creating the dosage form is to provide the therapeutic effect in the blood, to maintain it for a long time and to overcome changes. Some of the benefits of delayed release are: -

- Reduce the frequency of doses and eliminate incorrect doses, thus increasing patient compliance.
- Overcomes fluctuations in drug concentration in the blood and maintains consistent levels.
- Potent drugs can be controlled for safety by controlling their release.

Polymers (large molecules made up of many smaller repeating units) have many applications in the pharmaceutical industry and are of increasing importance. The properties of a polymer depend on its molecular weight, chain length and branching. Depending on solubility, polymers can be dissolved in water or organic solvents. Hydroxypropyl methylcellulose (HPMC) is one of the hydrophilic polymers due to its compatibility, better stability. HPMC is a cellulose derivative that forms a swelling gel on contact with water. Water penetration into the core matrix and subsequent drug release are controlled by the swollen gel layer. Chemical release from HPMC matrices is as follows:

- Diffusion
- Erosion
- Mixed release (combination of diffusion and erosion).

The extent of drug dissolution from the polymer matrix depends on the physicochemical properties of the active ingredient (API) and the nature and amount of excipients in the

formulation. Usually, the diffusion process is observed when hydrophilic substances are released. When water enters, the matrix swells and the solution dissolves and spreads out of the matrix at a predetermined rate. For hydrophobic drugs, drug release occurs after matrix erosion. Similarly, water-soluble excipients present in the tablet matrix first dissolve and form microchannels, which increases water penetration into the matrix core and improves dispersion. Many studies have reported that disintegration can be increased by increasing the amount of lactose (a water-soluble excipient) in the tablet matrix, and disintegration can be reduced by adding dicalcium phosphate (a water-soluble excipient agent). Changes in the GI tract also affect the separation process due to changes in enzyme activity and pH from neutral to acidic to alkaline. Alcohol has a solubilizing effect on HPMC, and the US Food and Drug Administration (FDA) has issued a warning about the rapid release of the drug from the matrix when alcohol is consumed [3].

Objectives

- ◆ To carry out preformulation study.
- ◆ To prepare sustained release matrix tablet.
- ◆ To perform in vitro study of sustained release tablet.

Advantages

- ◆ Simple to produce.
- ◆ Flexible, efficient, and reasonably priced.
- ◆ The longer therapeutic concentrations may be maintained by the sustained-release formulations.
- ◆ Utilizing formulations with a sustained release prevents high blood concentration.
- ◆ Formulations with sustain release still have the potential to increase patient compliance. Drug absorption can be slowed to lessen toxicity.
- ◆ Boost the drug's stability by shielding it from the gastrointestinal tract's hydrolysis or other derivative modifications.
- ◆ Reduce the negative local and systemic consequences.
- ◆ A rise in therapeutic effectiveness.
- ◆ Reduce medication build up with long-term dosage [4].

Disadvantages

- ◆ Delay in onset of action.
- ◆ Possibility of dose dumping due to food, physiological or formulation variables and thus increased risk of toxicity.
- ◆ Dose dumping.
- ◆ Higher cost of formulation.
- ◆ Reduced potential for dosage adjustment.

Mechanism of action

Tofacitinib is a selective inhibitor of the JAK kinase family and is highly selective for other kinases in the human genome. In a kinase assay, tofacitinib inhibits JAK1, JAK2, JAK3, and to a lesser extent tyrosine kinase 2 (TyK2).

Fig 3: JAK-STAT system in human cells

Tofacitinib preferentially inhibits the interaction of JAK3 and/or JAK1-associated heterodimeric receptors. The inhibitory effect of tofacitinib on JAK1 and JAK3 can block the

signaling of various cytokines through gamma chain receptors, including IL-2, -4, -7, -9, -15, and -21. These cytokines are important for lymphocyte activation, growth, and function, so inhibition of their signaling would lead to changes in many aspects of the immune system [5].

Fig 4: schematic representation of JAK/STAT pathway and role of JAK inhibitory drugs.

Tofacitinib Citrate Patented Formulations

Table 1: Marketed formulations of Tofacitinib Citrate

Brand name	Formulation	Dose	Company name
XELJANZ	Tablets	5 and 10 mg	Pfizer
XELJANZ XR	Extended release tablets	5 and 11 mg	Pfizer
XELJANZ	Oral solution	1mg/mL	Pfizer
Tofazak	Tablets	5 mg	Cipla Ltd
BETRECEP	Film coated tablets	5 mg	Pfizer
JAKNAT	Tablets	5 mg	Manufactured by MSN Laboratories Pvt. Ltd. Marketed by Natco Pharma Ltd
TOFASIG	Tablets	5 mg	Signature Phytochemical Limited
TNIB	Tablets	5 mg	Microlabs Limited
TOFADOZ	Tablets	5 mg	MSN Laboratories Pvt. Ltd.
TECT-NIB	Tablets	5 mg	Manufactured by MSN Laboratories Pvt. Ltd. Marketed by Ipca Laboratories Ltd
TOFATAS	Ointment	2% w/w, 10 mg	Intas Pharmaceuticals Limited
TOFANAC	Gel	2% w/w	Cynak Life Sciences

Tciticb	Gel	2% w/w	Sky Impex
TOFARUS	Gel	2% w/w	Cyrus Remedies

Materials

Polymers for sustained release tablets:

The most common polymers used to prepare matrix systems include hydrophilic and hydrophobic polymers.

- a) Hydrophilic polymers - primarily include hydroxypropyl methylcellulose (HPMC), hydroxyl Propyl cellulose (HPC), hydroxyethyl cellulose (HEC), xanthan gum, sodium alginate, poly(ethylene oxide) and cross-linked homopolymers and copolymers of acrylic acid.
- b) Hydrophobic polymers - formulations often include waxes and water-insoluble polymers.
- c) Natural polymers - xanthan gum, guar gum, sodium alginate, pectin, chitosan [6].

Formulation Method

Direct Compression: Direct compression consists of directly compressing powdered material into tablets. If the drug constitutes a significant portion of the total weight of the tablet, direct compression is used. Tablets containing 25% or less of the drug can be formulated with suitable drugs that act as carriers for the drug. The tablets prepared by the above process are placed in the tablet press, which may be one station or several stations [7].

Evaluation of Matrix Tablets

Physical parameters of tablets

Physical appearance and surface properties of tofacitinib matrix tablets were examined. The thickness and diameter of randomly selected tablets (n=10) were measured with a digital hardness (Monsanto) and thickness tester and the average values were calculated. To calculate the weight changes, tablets were selected individually, weighed and the average weight was measured. The difference between the weight of the tablet and the average weight is used to calculate the weight percentage using the following equation:

$$Percent\ weight\ variation = \frac{Individual\ weight - Average\ weight}{Average\ weight} \times 100$$

.....(4)

Thickness and Diameter

Thickness and diameter of tablets are determined using Vernier Caliper[6]. Check the physical dimensions of the tablets; the thickness of the dimension is important for customer satisfaction and tablet-to-tablet compatibility. Tablet diameter and punch size depend on the die and punch was selected as the drug[8].

Hardness of the Tablet

Tablet hardness is defined as the “force required to fracture a tablet in a diametral compression test.” Three tablets for each formulation were tested for hardness using a Monsanto hardness analyzer, end point is recognized by breaking the tablet [6].

Friability test

The friability of prepared tablets was determined by using Roche friabilator [9]. Weighing twenty tablets, we put them in the friabilator. At a speed of 25 rpm, the chamber is rotated for 4 minutes. After removing the tablets from the chamber, they are weighed. Losing weight is a sign of friability. If there is less than a 0.8% weight loss, the tablets should be regarded as being of good quality[6].

The percent friability calculate by using the following formula [10].

$$F = \frac{1-W}{W_0} \times 100$$

where, W_0 = Weight of the tablet before friability.

W = Weight of the tablet after friability

Test for weight variation

This is a crucial procedure that falls under the purview of quality control testing. According to standard, every tablet in a batch should weigh the same amount. To get the average weight, twenty pills are weighed and then the weight of a single tablet is compared. In accordance with specific Indian Pharmacopoeia, the % weight variation is calculated [6].

Determination of Drug content

Drug content is ascertained by dissolving the sample in an appropriate solvent, such as pH 7.4 phosphate buffer solution, and analyzing it using a visible spectrophotometer and the pure drug's standard calibration curve.

In Vitro Dissolution Testing

In vitro dissolution studies were performed on a USP Tablet Dissolution Tester Model 1 (Basket). Use up to 900 mL of phosphate buffer (without enzymes) as dissolution medium. Dissolution studies were performed for 24 hours. The temperature of the dissolution medium was maintained at 37 ± 0.5 °C. The paddle rotated at 75 rpm. Samples (5 mL) were withdrawn within 24 hours upon pre-order. Replace the old volume with fresh dissolution medium after each application to fully maintain the tank. The sample was diluted to the appropriate volume with phosphate buffer and absorbance was recorded at 273.5 nm using a UV spectrophotometer [11].

Conclusion

In summary, the development and testing of Tofacitinib citrate sustained release (SR) matrix tablets show encouraging promise for providing regulated drug release over time. These SR pills can lower dosage frequency, maintain therapeutic levels, and possibly improve patient adherence and therapeutic results by refining formulation characteristics. According to the evaluation results, Tofacitinib SR tablets can successfully maintain drug release when the matrix composition is appropriate. The safety, effectiveness, and long-term advantages of these formulations for chronic inflammatory disorders require more research, including clinical trials.

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